

Explore a new framework to evolve third space relationships

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Higher education research demonstrates the increasing relevance of the university third space metaphor to describe how people work together while crossing, disrupting, and transcending the boundaries of their respective roles and identities, thereby challenging the confines of organisational structure. Third-space working is characterised by diverse thinking, co-creating new practices, and challenging outdated systems and processes. It is often a space of professional tensions that working across boundaries inevitably produces.

Whether you navigate a professional/academic identity, work across the central organisational command centre or in a faculty, or experience tension at the intersection of teaching and research activities – you may be experiencing the “third space effect”.

This one-hour interactive session in the Slowposium aimed to challenge participants’ perceptions and inspire their third-space imaginations by presenting a four-phase framework for the evolution of professional interaction within changing boundary practices and identities. These phases combine work by Whitchurch (2012) and Veles (2023) which describe a practical pathway for re-imagining third space relationships, from Contestation to Reconciliation to Reconstruction and finally to Transformation.

In the second part of the session, participants applied this framework to real-world third-space scenarios, looking for new and desired futures. Participants were invited to engage in collective critical reflection about how the combination of third-space working, boundary learning and the collaborative capital of relationships and recognition of people’s contributions can be applied to and can shape contemporary and emerging university practices.

The session was conducted via Zoom and the recording of the session is available on YouTube [https://youtu.be/v8RE6_jX7bM]

Presentation

The dynamics of third space - advancing the framework of interactions from three to four phases

The image shows two book covers. On the left is 'Reconstructing Identities in Higher Education: THE RISE OF THIRD SPACE PROFESSIONALS' by Celia Whitchurch, published by SRHE. On the right is 'OPTIMISING THE THIRD SPACE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: CASE STUDIES OF INTERCULTURAL AND CROSS-BOUNDARY COLLABORATION' by Natalia Veles, published by Knowledge Research in Higher Education. A large pink arrow points from the left book to the right book.

Explored university activities (Whitchurch's research - 2010 and 2013 publications)

The image displays seven pink boxes arranged in two rows. The top row contains four boxes: 'Programme development', 'Widening participation', 'Community and business partnership', and 'Professional and academic practice'. The bottom row contains three boxes: 'Learning support', 'Institutional planning', and 'Communications and public relations'.

The framework of interactions - three distinct processes or phases (Whitchurch's research)

- ❖ *Contestation*
- ❖ *Reconciliation*
- ❖ *Reconstruction*

The image shows a photograph of three objects on a white surface: a white rectangular block, a white ring, and a light blue ring. To the right of the photograph is a list of three items, each preceded by a diamond symbol and italicized text.

Framework of interactions - CONTESTATION

- ❖ **Operational issues:** navigating operational challenges and processes associated with different ways and paces of working among academic and entrepreneurial approaches.
- ❖ **Contractual nature:** the clear, goal-oriented nature of privately funded work versus the more open-ended nature of academic projects.
- ❖ **Political issues:** the negotiations and political dynamics involved in public/private collaborations.
- ❖ **Perceptions of work:** various activities crossing public/private spaces are seen as “trade” or “dirty” work by some.
- ❖ **‘Resistance and struggle’** (Whitchurch, 2013, p. 26): common academic frustrations, such as management requirements and resource constraints; proliferation of the sense of ‘otherness’ and lack of understanding of one another and their respective work.

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Framework of interactions - RECONCILIATION

- ❖ **Potential of collaboration:** Encourages joint efforts between parties for mutual benefit.
- ❖ **Perceived added value:** Promotes initiatives that wouldn’t occur otherwise.
- ❖ **Ideological and material outcomes:** Aims to raise aspirations and improve opportunities.
- ❖ **Negotiation of differences:** Facilitates new identities and collaboration.
- ❖ **Dynamic in-between space:** Allows for innovative and unexpected activities.
- ❖ **Cultural translation:** Creates a safer space for new activities and relationships.
- ❖ **Critical exchange:** Restructures binary choices to open new alternatives.

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Framework of interactions - RECONSTRUCTION

- ❖ **Interaction and respect among academic colleagues.**
- ❖ **Freedom to produce appropriate solutions.**
- ❖ **Creation of the new “rules and resources” and setting up new structures of authority.**
- ❖ **This pluralistic environment is defined by terms like ‘partnership’, ‘capital building’, ‘networking’, and ‘creativity’.**
- ❖ **Individuals contribute to forming new plural spaces and developing new identities.**
- ❖ **Investment in both strong and weak ties with key individuals and networks is crucial.**
- ❖ **Institutional and professional growth opportunities mitigate the frustrations of the Contestation process.**

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Framework of interactions - SUMMARY

- ◊ The processes of Contestation, Reconciliation, and Reconstruction are interconnected.
- ◊ They can occur simultaneously, representing different stages in the development of activities and identities.
- ◊ Individuals may align with one process or display characteristics of multiple processes based on circumstances.
- ◊ These processes help describe the complex and multi-dimensional nature of working in third space environments highlighting both ideological commitment and disenchantment among individuals.

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University staff in collaborative third space environments - "Optimising the third space in higher education: Case studies of intercultural and cross-boundary collaboration" (Veles, 2023)

The alignment of the five third space projects and the core activity domains of teaching and learning, research and engagement

(developed from Whitchurch's [2008] university third space typology)

TUA = Tropical University, Australia
TUS = Tropical University, Singapore

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Case study example

The university project of entrepreneurial collaboration among three key actors:

- ◊ a scientist (the Academic)
- ◊ a technical solutions manager (the Innovator)
- ◊ a Research Business Manager (the Business Manager).

Veles, N. (2024). Critical thirding and third space collaboration: University professional staff and new type of knowledge production. *London Review of Education*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.14324/LRE.22.1.24>

Veles, N. (2022). *Optimising the third space in higher education: Case studies of intercultural and cross-boundary collaboration* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003259527>

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Extended framework of the dynamics of third space - TRANSFORMATION

- ◊ Learning at the boundaries must occur.
- ◊ Dialogical interaction and collaborative capital creation are involved.
- ◊ Three levels of transformation: can occur on institutional, interpersonal, intrapersonal, or on all three, levels.
- ◊ The integration of individual worldviews, perspectives, and personal and professional discoveries.
- ◊ Lasting transformation of processes and practices

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Extended framework of the dynamics of third space - Four Phases (Whitchurch's and Veles's research)

- ❖ Contestation
- ❖ Reconciliation
- ❖ Reconstruction
- ❖ Transformation

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Activity: Applying the principles in the workplace

Your university has decided to embark upon a major curriculum renewal project. This will involve an ongoing collaboration between academics in the history school and a group of academic developers, learning designers and educational technologists (collectively EdAdvisors).

The academics are sceptical of this project and question whether the EdAdvisors adequately understand what they are teaching and how they teach to make a useful contribution. They feel that if the EdAdvisors are to be helpful, they need to think and act much more like academics. This is the first time they have not had complete control of their curriculum process.

The EdAdvisors have reviewed the past courses and teaching feedback for the subjects involved and have some ideas for what might be changed, from a pedagogical and technological standpoint.

In breakout groups, what actions, based on what we have learned, might be used to move from contestation to reconciliation?

- By learning & teaching leaders?
- By academics
- By EdAdvisors

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Third space interactions - further provocations

“Third Space is...open, symbolic, playful, and generative. It can also be contested space if power differentials force confrontations between conceptual systems” and yet, “the possibilities of Third Space challenge us to reconsider our professional priorities and concepts.” (Elmborg, 2011, p. 345).

- How can individuals mobilise third-space learning and work to achieve genuine transformations?
- How will technology continue to shape third-space thinking and working across third-space environments?
- How could we, third space professionals, apply the knowledge of the phases of interaction productively and across various collaborative projects and activities?

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The university third space is:

the “emergence of broadly based, extended projects across the university, which are no longer containable within firm boundaries, and have created new portfolios of activity.”

Whitchurch (2015, 2022)

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The university third space further interpreted as:

“a relatively new approach that has intriguing implications for how work changes where clear professional boundaries dissolve”

Verbaan and Cox (2014)

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